

6 5 4 3 2 1

Top View
Scale 1:18

Isometric View
Scale 1:18

Front View
Scale 1:18

Right Side View
Scale 1:18

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:			DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES			DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION			
All the dimensions are in mm.										<p>CartFrame</p>				
DRAWN	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE										TITLE:	
CHK'D	Ayan													
APPV'D														
MFG														
Q.A														